

Learning Network Flow Control Strategies from Miles-In-Trail Data

Nianxi Xie, Yanjun Wang
 College of Civil Aviation
 Nanjing Uni. of Aero. and Astro.
 Nanjing, China
 {xienianxi,ywang}@nuaa.edu.cn

Ying Zhou, Sameer Alam, Vu Duong
 ATMRI
 Nanyang Technical University
 Singapore
 ying010@e.ntu.edu.sg, {sameeralam, vu.duong}@ntu.edu.sg

Mark Hansen
 Department of CEE
 UC Berkeley
 Berkeley CA, USA
 mhansen@berkeley.edu

Abstract—Miles-In-Trail (MIT) is a widely used Traffic Management Initiative (TMI) to manage the imbalance between airspace demand and capacity, alleviating congestion. However, human expert-driven MIT decision-making faces challenges in complex environments, particularly in multi-airport regions. To address this, we propose a two-stage MIT issuance prediction model. In the first stage, three scenarios are explored to analyze the mechanisms behind single- and multi-airport waypoint selection in depth. This model predicts the waypoint combinations requiring MIT issuance, which then serve as input for the second stage. In the second stage, three models are compared to refine MIT predictions for each waypoint under specific constraints, optimizing flow control strategies. The two-stage model’s performance is also compared to a one-stage direct prediction using the LSTM model. An empirical analysis of two major airports in the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macau Greater Bay Area demonstrates that the two-stage model significantly enhances prediction performance. Specifically, the average improvements in Precision_{macro}, Recall_{macro}, and F1_{macro} for key waypoints were 6.455%, 10.245%, and 10.254%, respectively. Based on these results, we identify key factors influencing MIT issuance and provide guidance for selecting MIT values, improving MIT implementation efficiency in multi-airport regions and offering a scientific foundation for air traffic flow management in complex airspace.

Keywords—Miles-In-Trail; machine learning; air traffic flow management

I. INTRODUCTION

With the growing global demand for air travel, the management of air traffic has become more complex. Challenges such as flight delays, airspace congestion, and capacity resource distribution have increased the strain on air traffic control systems (ATC) [1]. Air Traffic Flow Management (ATFM) plays a critical role in ensuring efficient and safe airspace operation by regulating aircraft movements to prevent overloading ATC capacity. Through the implementation of a broad set of proactive strategies, ATFM not only ensures the safety of air traffic but also enhances operational efficiency and flight reliability, thereby facilitating more smooth and predictable traffic management, even as traffic demand increases.

Air traffic flow management systems have been widely implemented around the world, each designed to address

the specific operational needs of different airspaces, traffic complexities, and technological capabilities. Notable examples include the FAA Air Traffic Control System Command Center, network manager in Europe, and the National air Traffic Flow Management (NTFM) system in China. These systems can implement strategies that are all grounded in data-driven methodologies enhancing the safety, efficiency, and reliability of global air traffic operations. ATFM initiatives are particularly crucial in addressing the growing challenge of demand-capacity imbalances, a concern that has become more pronounced as air traffic volumes increase, especially in congested airspace and at major hubs. Traffic Management Initiatives (TMI)—such as Miles-in-Trail (or Minutes-in-Trail), Ground Delay Programs (GDP), Airspace Flow Programs (AFP), and Ground Stops (GS)—are essential tools used by air traffic flow management units to maintain a balance between capacity and demand [2]. Among these, MIT has emerged as a widely adopted strategy, particularly in China, where it is extensively employed to regulate spatial separation among aircraft in high-traffic regions [3], [4]. As congestion intensifies, MIT plays a pivotal role in mitigating delays and optimizing airspace utilization. By integrating predictive modeling and real-time data adjustments, MIT measures effectively streamline traffic flows, reduce bottlenecks, and ensure operational safety. Beyond managing spatial constraints, efficient implementation of MIT also has broader implications, influencing key performance metrics such as on-time performance, resource allocation, and overall network efficiency. Incorporating predictive techniques into MIT decision making not only enhances flow management but also improves delay handling, thus strengthening the overall effectiveness of air traffic operations.

Research in Air Traffic Flow Management dates back to the early 1970s, when early studies focused mainly on traditional scheduling algorithms and basic rule-based systems designed to address the persistent imbalance between demand and capacity in aviation systems [5]–[7]. With rapid advances in computing technology and the increasing availability of aviation data, research evolved to focus on optimizing traffic management strategies, including the development of more sophisticated traffic management models through techniques

such as linear programming [8], dynamic programming [9], and heuristic algorithms [10]. In recent years, the emergence of big data technologies and artificial intelligence has shifted the research focus towards more granular demand forecasting, real-time airspace capacity management, and integrated network optimization approaches. This transition has fueled a surge in studies exploring the application of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) methods within the ATFM domain. For example, researchers have leveraged historical flight data, weather information, and airport operations data to train ML models, enhancing the accuracy and responsiveness of demand forecasting [11]–[13]. Currently, much of the research is centered on the comprehensive optimization of flight demand prediction, airspace capacity management, and traffic flow management strategies—particularly GDP. Although various prediction models for GDPs have been proposed, these plans are generally tailored to specific airports and often follow standardized structures. MIT is different from GDP in that its flow control involves the setting of numerous waypoints and specific MIT value, in particular managing air traffic within a network involving multiple waypoints and airports introduces additional complexities. In such contexts, shared waypoints and interactions between airports complicate the accurate setting of values. Air traffic flow management personnel often face two major challenges: First, airspace conditions being better than anticipated, the separation value set by MIT are overly conservative, resulting in unnecessary resource wastage; second, in cases where airspace conditions deteriorate beyond expectations, the separation value defined by MIT are inadequate, posing potential risks to airspace safety [14]. These challenges highlight the need for more flexible and dynamic solutions to manage air traffic flow in increasingly complex airspace environments [15].

In practice, MITs often lead to unnecessary delays [16], particularly when flights are directed to multiple airports and require MITs for flow control management. Accurately predicting the specific route points where MITs should be issued, as well as determining the optimal MIT value for these restrictions, is crucial for minimizing delays and enhancing operational efficiency. This paper addresses these challenges by introducing a two-stage predictive model for MIT. In the first stage, the model identifies combinations of waypoints where MIT restrictions are likely to be imposed, based on the intended arrival airports of the flights. Building on these predictions, the second stage determines the distribution of MIT value to be assigned to the relevant waypoints. This two-stage approach ensures a structured, data-driven prediction of both the locations where MIT restrictions will be issued and their corresponding MIT value. By integrating real-time data and machine learning techniques, this research aims to improve the accuracy and effectiveness of MIT implementation, ultimately reducing delays and optimizing air traffic flow within the National Airspace System (NAS).

The structure of this paper is as follows. Section II covers the data sources, feature engineering for the MIT two-stage predictive model, and examines the MIT implementation frequencies and value, introducing the airports and waypoints

under study. Section III describes the research methods. Section IV reports on the experimental results, including discussion and analysis. Section V concludes with limitations and suggestions for future research.

II. DATA PREPROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

A. Data

This research aims to develop a two-stage predictive model for the implementation of MIT to regulate traffic flow in a multi-airport system in China. The specific sets of airports and waypoints investigated are denoted as A and P respectively, where $A=\{ZGGG, ZGSZ\}$ and $P=\{GYA, AVBEP, NOLON, DUDIT, NUSPA, IRNOR, P154, P599, P600, P319\}$. The model leverages historical data derived from three extensive datasets:

- **Airport Operational Data:** This study focuses mainly on Guangzhou Baiyun International Airport (ICAO code: ZGGG) and Shenzhen Baoan Airport (ICAO code: ZGSZ). It incorporates historical flight data, including the actual waypoints, actual and planned takeoff and landing times, TMIs, and other relevant data, from March 1, 2023, to July 31, 2023.
- **Airport Weather Data:** METAR reports provide weather data for ZGGG and ZGSZ every half-hour from March 1, 2023, to July 31, 2023. These meteorological data are sourced from METAR reports, which include several critical meteorological components: wind direction and speed, visibility, runway visibility range, weather conditions, cloud cover, temperature and dew point, mean sea level, and weather changes, etc.
- **National Traffic Flow Management Data:** National TMIs includes TMI types (e.g. GDP, MIT, AFP, GS), along with details such as issued/start/end times, issuing and receiving ATFM units, required and provided facilities, and pass-back information, from March 1, 2023, to July 31, 2023. In the MIT value, given the diversity of MIT value observed in the historical data, such as once every 5 minutes, twice every 15 minutes, four times every 15 minutes, etc., we chose to use the average MIT value for each aircraft subjected to MIT for comparison.

B. Feature engineering

To accurately predict the specific waypoints for the implementation of MIT and their corresponding values, we constructed the feature space based on existing studies and the actual factors [17] influencing the implementation of MIT. These factors are detailed in the subsections and summarized in Table I, which outline the features used in the first and second stage models, respectively. The original data sets are preprocessed into the following time series data with a granularity of 30 minutes, dividing the entire day into 48 intervals. Denoting the time index as t , we define the set T as $T = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 48\}$.

- 1) **ATMAP score (Ω_t^k):** The ATMAP score at certain place k (an airport or a waypoint) at time t is defined as Ω_t^k , where $k \in A \cup P$. It is calculated based on the ATMAP algorithm, which is commonly used to quantify the

effects of weather conditions on airport operation [18]. The ATMAP algorithm divides weather conditions into 5 categories: visibility, wind, precipitation, freezing, and hazardous weather phenomena, each of which has a different level of severity, and ultimately calculates a weather score.

- 2) *Arrival demand* (D_t^a): The arrival demand at airport a at time t is estimated using airport operations data, along with the planned arrival time records for each flight.
- 3) *Waypoint capacity* (C_t^p): Leveraging the actual crossing waypoints times recorded in the national flight data, the historical maximum traffic at waypoint p at time t was computed to determine the waypoint capacity.
- 4) *GDP Implementation* (I_t^a): From National Traffic Flow Management data, we find that several flights may suffer GDP and MIT restrictions. In such cases, the implementation of these TMIs together imposes dual constraints on these flights, considerably affecting the predictive accuracy of MIT-related forecasts. This highlights the importance of integrating GDP status as a vital feature in the forecasting model to improve its reliability and robustness [11]. Here, I_t^a is a binary variable, with $I_t^a = 1$ indicates a GDP is issued at airport a at time t , while $I_t^a = 0$ indicates that no GDP is issued at airport a at time t .
- 5) *Queueing delay* (τ_t^a): We use the cumulative actual arrivals minus planned arrivals queuing diagram to calculate deterministic arrival delays at airport a at time t . In a deterministic queuing system, delays occur when demand exceeds capacity over a given period, requesting flow managers to issue flow control measures to minimize congestion. Thus, queueing delay is incorporated as a key feature in the model.

Trigonometric functions are used to encode the cyclical nature of temporal data, including the month, weekday, hour, and day of the month.

For hourly data within a 24-hour cycle, the functions $\sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{24}\right)$ and $\cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{24}\right)$ are employed, ensuring that 24:00 (midnight) and 01:00 are adjacent, thus maintaining hourly continuity. Similarly, for longer time spans like the month, day of the week, and day of the month, trigonometric transformations with periods of 12, 7, and up to 31 are used, guaranteeing smooth transitions between time units [19].

C. Analysis of implemented MITs

Between March 1 and July 31, 2023, a total of 64 ATFM units across China mainland has issued 24,200 traffic flow management initiatives, with MIT restrictions accounting for 21,186 (87.5%).

We engaged in discussions with traffic flow managers responsible for issuing MITs for traffic flows and found that accurate MIT value determination continues to pose substantial technical challenges. During our initial research, we performed a cluster analysis of the MIT value. The results of this clustering indicate variations in the MIT value even under identical conditions. By examining the histograms and cumulative distribution frequency plots of the MIT value, illustrated in Fig.1, we found a finer level of differentiation

Figure 1: Histogram and CDF of MIT value

when the value ranged between 1 and 10, accompanied by a notably higher frequency of releases, which makes up over 85% of total MITs. When the MIT value is set between 0 and 15 minutes, it accounts for more than 95% of the total historical release frequency. Releases with value exceeding 15 minutes are relatively rare, typically occurring only under extreme circumstances.

From March 1 to July 31, 2023, Guangzhou Baiyun airport and Shenzhen Bao'an Airport were the two largest airports impacted by MIT restrictions among the airports with flight disruptions. Specifically, these airports recorded 54,665 and 43,896 flights under MIT restrictions. Therefore, this study examines the waypoints at which flights arrived at airports within the Greater Bay Area (GBA) of Guangdong, Hong Kong, and Macao under MIT restrictions. We analyze the flights arriving at Guangzhou Baiyun Airport and Shenzhen Bao'an Airport to identify which flights were subject to MIT restrictions and to determine the most frequently restricted waypoints.

Fig. 2 shows ten specific waypoints studied in this paper, which are frequently controlled waypoints for flights arrival at ZGGG and ZGSZ airports. These waypoints are located in Guangdong Province and its neighboring provinces, with GYA and NOLON serving as entry points into GBA area.

Figure 2: Locations and frequencies of MIT implemented at the waypoints around GBA area.

TABLE I. Variables in the Two-Stage Prediction Model

Notation	Description
T	Set of time indices of time series data. $T = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 48\}$.
t	time index of time series data, $t \in T$.
A	Set of airports investigated in this work. $A = \{ZGGG, ZGSZ\}$.
P	Set of waypoints investigated in this work. $P = \{GYA, AVBEP, NOLON, DUDIT, NUSPA, IRNOR, P154, P599, P600, P319\}$.
Ω_t^k	The ATMAP score at a certain place k (can be an airport or a waypoint) at time t , where $k \in A \cup P$.
D_t^a	The number of flights scheduled to arrive at a specific airport a at time t , where $a \in A$.
τ_t^a	The queuing delay at a given airport a at time t , defined as the difference between scheduled and actual arrival times, where $a \in A$.
I_t^a	Indicator of whether GDP (Ground Delay Program) control measures are applied at time t , where $a \in A$.
C_t^p	Historical maximum flow rates for waypoints p at time t , where $p \in P$.
N	The output result of the first stage model prediction (Task III) is the waypoint combination number.

III. METHODOLOGY

Here, we provide details on the development of the two-stage predictive model. The model has two main functions: (i) to predict which waypoints an MIT should be issued (locations), and (ii) the MIT value (magnitude).

Fig. 3 illustrates the conceptual framework of the proposed two-stage predictive model. It consists of two main components. The first stage can help air traffic flow managers in selecting the best waypoints to impose MIT constraints. The result from the first-stage model is a forecast of waypoint combinations for each half-hour period. We consider three different scenarios:

- Scenario 1 (S_1): MIT implemented for aircraft landing at ZGGG only
- Scenario 2 (S_2): MIT implemented for aircraft landing at ZGSZ only
- Scenario 3 (S_3): MIT implemented for aircraft landing at both ZGGG and ZGSZ

The second-stage model, building on the first-stage model's outcomes (Task III), predicts MIT value for each predicted waypoint with MIT issuance. The predicted MIT values offer a reference for flow managers to make decisions in specific operating environments, enhancing the efficiency of MIT implementations.

To ensure the model's outputs are operationally meaningful, it is essential to incorporate domain-specific knowledge of air traffic management, particularly the application of Miles-in-Trail (MIT) as a critical flow control measure. MIT is used to regulate aircraft sequencing and maintain safe separation, especially in high-traffic terminal areas surrounding major airports such as Guangzhou Baiyun (ZGGG) and Shenzhen Bao'an (ZGSZ). By accounting for factors like airspace capacity, weather variability, and aircraft performance, the model's predictions remain both data-driven and operationally relevant. This integration of expert knowledge enhances the model's practicality and supports more adaptive and efficient MIT strategies in dynamic traffic environments.

A. The first-stage model: MIT waypoint prediction

The first-stage model is designed to predict waypoint combinations for issuing MIT. Compared to previous studies treating waypoints separately, this method better reflects real-world practice, as confirmed by interviews with Chinese air

traffic flow managers, enhancing its potential significance in supporting decision-making in real-world scenarios. In addition, unlike independent waypoint predictions, this method captures the interdependence among the waypoints. For each waypoint, we consider two states to indicate whether MIT is issued or not. Let 0 denote the state of No-MIT and 1 denote the state of Issuing-MIT. Using three waypoints as an example, there are eight possible combinations: 000, 010, 100, 001, 110, 011, 101, and 111. We employ one-hot encoding for these statuses, producing distinct vectors for each scenario. Then we can define the waypoints combination prediction problem as a multi-class classification task.

In MIT issuing, the states in previous time steps largely influence the current and future states. To capture these temporal dependencies, we use the LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory Network) model [20], which is particularly effective for time series prediction. Compared with the standard recurrent neural network (RNN) model, it can handle long-term dependencies by addressing the vanishing gradient problem. In the first stage, 12 prior time steps (from $t-12$ to $t-1$) are used to predict the next step (t). By tuning the hyperparameters, the best architecture of LSTM model consists of a 64-unit LSTM layer, a 0.2 Dropout layer to reduce overfitting, and fully connected layers (128, 256, 128, 64 neurons) with ReLU as activations function. A final Dense layer with softmax activation outputs class probabilities for multi-class classification.

B. The second-stage model: MIT value prediction

The results produced in the first-stage (Task III) are used as inputs for the second-stage model, which predicts the MIT value for each waypoint in the state of issuing-MIT. Temporal dependencies are still important in the second stage. However, the limited training data (fewer than 200 samples) in the second-stage prediction poses challenges for the models requiring long time-series inputs in capturing meaningful patterns, potentially reducing prediction accuracy. To mitigate this, we employ alternative algorithms such as Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM, which are better suited for learning from small datasets and making reliable predictions.

A brief overview of the three prediction models is provided below.

Figure 3: The diagram of the two-stage prediction model

- 1) **Random Forest(RF)** : Random Forest is an ensemble learning method based on Bagging. It improves predictive performance by training multiple decision trees in parallel and aggregating their results. This approach effectively reduces model variance and mitigates overfitting risks, making it particularly well-suited for small-scale datasets. Its random feature selection mechanism enhances model robustness and provides good interpretability.
- 2) **XGBoost** : XGBoost, a gradient boosting framework based on Boosting, sequentially optimizes decision trees to minimize the loss function. Despite the small size of the dataset, XGBoost's regularization mechanism and subsampling strategy effectively control overfitting, while its efficient implementation enables strong performance on classification tasks with small datasets.
- 3) **LightGBM** : LightGBM is another efficient algorithm based on Boosting, which utilizes a Leaf-wise growth strategy and histogram-based algorithms, significantly enhancing training efficiency. Its design is particularly well-suited for handling large-scale data, but with proper tuning, it can also deliver strong performance on small datasets. LightGBM's efficiency and native support for categorical features enable it to remain competitive even with limited data.

In the second stage, since the MIT values are non-continuous and there is limited variation in historical published MIT values (e.g., 5, 8, 15), a categorical prediction model is used. To improve the performance of the two-stage predictive model, a 5-fold cross-validation approach is used in each

training session to determine the best hyper-parameters. These selected hyper-parameters are then used to train the models on the full training dataset, and their performance is thoroughly evaluated on the test dataset.

C. Data resampling

As demonstrated in Table II, each airport exhibits a class imbalance, with class of MIT implementation appearing less frequently than no MIT restriction. Models trained on imbalanced datasets typically tend to favor the majority class. To address this challenge, SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) is employed to achieve a balanced dataset. The purpose of resampling is to enhance the prediction accuracy of the minor categories by equalizing the category distribution within the dataset, ensuring that the model can learn from each category during training. The resampling strategy is designed based on the ratio distribution of the original data, such as a sample ratio of 8: 5: 5: 3: 1. This approach helps to prevent excessive resampling, which could lead to overfitting.

TABLE II. Number of data points with and without MIT restrictions in each of scenario

Class	S_1	S_2	S_3
No MIT restriction	6922	6862	6747
MIT restriction	279	339	454

D. Training and testing set

The data from the case study is divided into a training set and a testing set. We organize the data chronologically, dedicating 80% to the training dataset and 20% to the testing dataset.

E. Evaluation metrics

MIT Released and MIT Not Released in S_1, S_2, S_3 , 4.03%, 4.94%, 6.72%. Given the extremely imbalanced data, accuracy may be skewed by the majority class, failing to reflect minority class performance. To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, we also consider precision, recall, and F1 score. Metrics are averaged using the Macro average, treating all classes equally without weighting by sample size. The evaluation metrics and their calculations are as follows:

- **TP (True Positive)**: Correctly predicted positives.
 - **TN (True Negative)**: Correctly predicted negatives.
 - **FP (False Positive)**: Negatives incorrectly predicted as positives.
 - **FN (False Negative)**: Positives incorrectly predicted as negatives.
 - **N**: The total number of categories.
- 1) **Accuracy**: The proportion of correct predictions:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

2) **Macro Precision**: Macro precision is averaged for each category after Precision is calculated separately:

$$\text{Precision}_{\text{macro}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} \quad (2)$$

3) **Macro recall**: The macro recall is averaged for each category after the recall is calculated separately:

$$\text{Recall}_{\text{macro}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i} \quad (3)$$

4) **Macro F1**: The macro F1 scores were averaged for each category after the F1 scores (the harmonic average of precision and recall) were calculated separately:

$$F1_{\text{macro}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{2 \times \text{Precision}_i \times \text{Recall}_i}{\text{Precision}_i + \text{Recall}_i} \quad (4)$$

In the two-stage model, the previously mentioned indicators are employed to assess how accurate MIT predictions are and the MIT value settings.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Experiments setup

1) *Experiment I: Predicting which waypoints are issuing MIT*: To gain a deeper understanding of the waypoint selection mechanism in single- and multi-airport scenarios, we performed three prediction tasks in the first stage.

- **Task I**: Task I is a prediction experiment for which waypoints MIT is released at when a flight lands at ZGGG. The input variables to the model are Ω_t^p, D_t^a, C_t^p , and I_t^a , where $p \in \{\text{AVBEP, P154, NOLON, GYA, NUSPA, DUDIT, P319, IRNOL, P599, P600}\}$, $a \in \{\text{ZGGG}\}$. This prediction involves 7 waypoints for scenario S_1 , each with two possible states (released: 1, unreleased: 0), resulting in $2^7 = 128$ possible combinations. It identifies which waypoint is imposed the MIT during the specified timeframe.

• **Task II**: Task II is a prediction experiment for which waypoints MIT is released at when a flight lands at ZGSZ. The input variables to the model are Ω_t^p, D_t^a, C_t^p , and I_t^a , where $p \in \{\text{AVBEP, P154, NOLON, GYA, IRNOL, P599, P600}\}$, $a \in \{\text{ZGSZ}\}$. Similar to Task I, this task also involves 7 waypoints for scenario S_2 .

- **Task III**: Task III is a prediction experiment for which waypoints MIT is released at when a flight lands at ZGGG and ZGSZ. The input variables to the model are Ω_t^p, D_t^a, C_t^p , and I_t^a , where $p \in \{\text{AVBEP, P154, NOLON, GYA, NUSPA, DUDIT, P319, IRNOL, P599, P600}\}$, $a \in \{\text{ZGGG, ZGSZ}\}$. This prediction combines the waypoints from Task I and II, expanding the total to 10 waypoints for the scenario S_3 . With each waypoint having two possible states, there are $2^{10} = 1024$ combinations. This model forecasts MIT constraints in a multi-airport scenario, identifying which waypoints released the MIT during the specified timeframe.

2) *Experiment II: Predicting MIT value*: The second stage model focuses on forecasting the distribution of MIT value for four key waypoints: NOLON, P154, AVBEP, and GYA. When the flight landed at ZGGG or ZGSZ, MIT restrictions were frequently imposed at the four waypoints located in Guangdong Province, which are shared by both airports. Notably, GYA and NOLON serve as critical entry points to the GBA area, emphasizing their strategic importance in regional air traffic management. In contrast, P154 and AVBEP share a historical association with flow-control measures, often having MIT restrictions issued simultaneously. This synchronized issuance reflects their collaborative role in managing air traffic flow within the region. The input variables to the model are $\Omega_t^p, D_t^a, C_t^p, \tau_t^a, N$ and I_t^a , where $p \in \{\text{AVBEP, P154, NOLON, GYA}\}$, $a \in \{\text{ZGGG, ZGSZ}\}$. The model's output corresponds to the specific MIT value setting. Historically, AVBEP has four MIT value categories, GYA nine, NOLON seven, and P154 four, including 0 values.

To further assess the accuracy of the two-stage model proposed in this study for predicting MIT value, we conducted an additional experiment using a direct, single-stage LSTM model. The setup parameters of this model were identical to those of the first-stage model, with the key distinction being that only a single waypoint feature was used as input, and the output was a predicted MIT value. The input variables to the model include $\Omega_t^p, D_t^a, C_t^p, \tau_t^a$ and I_t^a , where $p \in \{\text{AVBEP, P154, NOLON, GYA}\}$, $a \in \{\text{ZGGG, ZGSZ}\}$. The model's output corresponds to the specific MIT value setting. A predicted value of zero indicates that no MIT restriction was issued at the waypoint, while any non-zero prediction signifies the issuance of an MIT restriction, along with the corresponding MIT value setting.

We compared the evaluation metrics from the second-stage

of our two-stage model with those obtained from the direct MIT value prediction approach. This comparison enabled a deeper analysis of the effectiveness and robustness of the proposed methodology.

B. Results

1) *Results for Experiment I:* Table III provides a summary of the $\text{Precision}_{\text{macro}}$, $\text{Recall}_{\text{macro}}$, and F1_{macro} achieved for each prediction task when tuned with optimal hyperparameter settings.

TABLE III. Performance of the first stage model

Experiments	$\text{Precision}_{\text{macro}}$	$\text{Recall}_{\text{macro}}$	F1_{macro}
Task I	0.9150	0.9101	0.9109
Taks II	0.8769	0.9068	0.8874
Task III	0.8619	0.8837	0.8644

Task I and task II focus on MIT implementation predictions for single-airport scenarios, specifically targeting flights arriving at either ZGGG or ZGSZ. In contrast, task III extends the scope to the multi-airport scenarios, requiring the model to consider interactions and dependencies between multiple airports. This broader focus introduces additional complexities, such as shared air traffic flow, regional GDP effects, and the challenges of coordinating schedules across airports, making it more difficult to achieve the same performance levels as in single-airport forecasts.

In our comprehensive review of the prediction metrics, we notice specific patterns in $\text{precision}_{\text{macro}}$, $\text{Recall}_{\text{macro}}$, and F1_{macro} . F1_{macro} calculates and averages the F1 scores for each class, considering both precision and recall. It is particularly suitable for evaluating imbalanced datasets as it does not favor the majority class. Therefore, this paper emphasizes the analysis of the F1_{macro} metric. Task I achieves a top F1_{macro} of 0.9109, underscoring the model’s capability to consistently identify waypoint combinations within a single-airport context with negligible variation. For Task II, F1_{macro} slightly drops to 0.8874, indicating additional uncertainties even with a single airport focus. Task III, which records an F1_{macro} of 0.8644, highlights the challenges of modeling interactions across multiple airports. The other two evaluation metrics exhibit similar score patterns.

This research highlights the need to tailor predictive models to align with the specific scope and complexity of the operational environment. In scenarios involving multiple airports, enhancements like the integration of additional contextual features or the use of sophisticated modeling strategies for interactions among airports can substantially improve the efficacy of the model.

We employ gradient-based feature importance to analyze the top features for each prediction model, as presented in Fig. 4. The results highlight the varying significance of features across models, emphasizing factors that influence predictions in both single and multi-airport scenarios. The weather conditions at waypoints have a relatively minor impact on the forecast results, whereas the projected arrival demand at airports and the capacity of each waypoint have a more significant influence on the forecasts. Key waypoints, such

as GYA, NOLON, and AVBEP, must be closely monitored by air traffic flow managers, especially during peak demand or emergencies, to mitigate congestion. The planned arrival demand at airports such as ZGGG and ZGSZ is critical for MIT prediction, particularly in multi-airport regions where interconnected traffic affects regional flow management. Furthermore, the overlap of flow control measures including GDP and MIT complicates accurate MIT prediction, underscoring the need to consider multiple strategies.

Fig. 5 further explores the impact of the waypoint capacity features on Task III, with the circle size reflecting the influence of each waypoint on predictive performance. Waypoints closer to the GBA area tend to have a more significant influence on predictive performance. However, despite being geographically closer, P154 exhibits relatively low importance. Historical data analysis reveals that MIT measures for P154 and AVBEP are often implemented together, as the proximity of these two waypoints allows AVBEP to alleviate some of the congestion at P154. In contrast, NOLON and GYA are both entry points into the GBA; however, GYA, being a critical entry point for westbound flights, serves as the primary gateway for many flights, while NOLON, with nearby alternative entry points, benefits from additional capacity to mitigate congestion.

In conclusion, MIT flow control measures result from the interaction of waypoint demand, scheduled arrivals, and other flow control mechanisms, which requires a comprehensive strategy to optimize traffic forecasts and flow management.

Figure 5: Impact of waypoint capacity on task III

2) *Results for Experiment II:* Table IV presents the detailed evaluation metrics of the second-stage model, which uses three different techniques—Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM—for predicting MIT value, and compares them with the performance of the one-step LSTM model that directly predicts the MIT value. In the second-stage model, the output from the first-stage model (Task III), i.e., the waypoint combination number, is used as one of the input variables. The results show that the two-stage model significantly improves predictive performance compared to directly forecasting the MIT value for specific waypoints. We selected the models that perform best from Random

Figure 4: Feature importance scores for three prediction tasks

Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM to compare with the one-stage LSTM model, evaluating their performance in three key metrics: Precision_{macro}, Recall_{macro}, and F1_{macro}. Our analysis reveals that, on average, precision increased by 6.455% (ranging from 5.083% to 9.034%), recall improved by 10.245% (ranging from 8.135% to 12.003%), and F1 score rose by 10.254% (ranging from 7.883% to 13.117%) across four waypoints (AVBEP, P154, NOLON, and GYA). These findings emphasize the importance of considering waypoint interactions in MIT value prediction, which enhances the model’s reliability and provides a scientific foundation for air traffic flow managers when making MIT decisions, ultimately preventing the waste of airspace resources. Additionally, the results indicate that, due to the varying types of MIT value published at different waypoints in the historical data, the predictive performance differs slightly across waypoints. Specifically, the predictive performance for NOLON, AVBEP, and P154 surpasses that for GYA.

Among the methods, LightGBM emerged as the best performer. The subpar predictive performance for the GYA waypoint was investigated, revealing that subjective differences among flow managers under similar conditions affect its historical MIT value, leading to prediction bias. Furthermore, historical data reflect frequent, minor changes at the GYA point, and limited sample data insufficiently capture this variability, hindering the model’s predictive capability. Thus, future research will focus on the data characteristics of GYA-like waypoints, seeking tailored methods to boost predictive performance.

Using the predicted outcomes of the MIT value range from the second stage model, flow managers are able to dynamically modify the MIT by considering real-time variations in weather, waypoints, and airport traffic flow, leading to a more precise MIT configuration strategy. Furthermore, predictions from the two-stage model equip flow managers with a robust array of flow management tools to monitor conditions at airports, sectors, and waypoints in real time, enhance flow control operations, minimize superfluous flight delays, and ultimately optimize the utilization of airspace resources.

C. Discussion

The first stage model focuses on accurately predicting the arrival waypoints for flights in three distinct scenarios: a single airport at ZGGG, a single airport at ZGSZ, and a combined scenario involving both the ZGGG and ZGSZ airports. The F1_{macro} for these three tasks were 0.9109, 0.8874, and 0.8644, respectively. The inherent complexity of flight routes and the fluctuating traffic in multi-airport environments present considerable forecasting challenges. In the second stage of our research, we incorporated the waypoint combination number from the first stage as an input variable for the second stage model. Comparison with direct prediction of the MIT value in one step using the LSTM model showed that Precision_{macro}, Recall_{macro}, and F1_{macro} metrics for the four key waypoints studied above improved by an average of 6.455%, 10.245% and 10.254%. These findings underscore the importance of the first-stage output (Task III) in enhancing the second-stage model’s predictive performance. However, it remains essential to address waypoints such as GYA, where predictive performance is relatively low. Future research should focus on refining the model architecture, introducing additional influential variables, and expanding the dataset to improve the predictive performance for such waypoints. This approach aims to strengthen scientific decision-making in managing complex airspace traffic. By refining MIT application techniques, the model can help reduce delays and enhance operational efficiency, establishing it as an advanced decision-support tool. Moreover, it lays the foundation for further research into waypoint dependencies in multi-airport environments, thus improving both forecasting precision and the effectiveness of air traffic operations.

To regulate network flow, MITs are implemented at critical nodes of the airspace network by various traffic management units. This process represents a distributed network flow control problem, where the selection of waypoints and the determination of MIT value are critical for maintaining system efficiency and operational safety. The research findings indicate that waypoints experiencing high traffic volumes or recurrent bottlenecks, such as GYA and NOLON in terminal

TABLE IV. Model Evaluation Metrics for Waypoints

Waypoint	Precision _{macro}				Recall _{macro}				F1 _{macro}			
	RF	XGB	LGBM	LSTM	RF	XGB	LGBM	LSTM	RF	XGB	LGBM	LSTM
AVBEP	0.9252	0.9293	0.9222	0.8523	0.8092	0.9091	0.9098	0.8123	0.8495	0.9027	0.9081	0.8028
P154	0.8341	0.8546	0.8941	0.8476	0.7083	0.8200	0.8414	0.7781	0.7377	0.8158	0.8540	0.7916
NOLON	0.7199	0.7933	0.8000	0.7613	0.6686	0.7898	0.8003	0.7292	0.6439	0.7825	0.7921	0.7288
GYA	0.7893	0.8338	0.8296	0.7850	0.5962	0.7623	0.7402	0.6862	0.6369	0.7751	0.7574	0.6962

approach sectors, are prioritized for MIT implementation. Additionally, the anticipated arrival demand at the target airport significantly influences waypoint selection, with regions exhibiting higher demand fluctuations being more likely to trigger MIT deployment. Furthermore, the implementation of GDP at airports also impacts MIT issuance, as these measures interact with en-route flow control strategies. Through the first-stage prediction model, waypoint combinations with significant synergistic effects are identified, such as P599-P600 and AVBEP-P154. Coordinated management of these combinations effectively mitigates localized congestion and improves airspace utilization efficiency. This study employs a two-stage joint prediction model to significantly improve the accuracy of MIT value settings. Experimental results demonstrate that the synergistic effects of waypoint combinations significantly influence the determination of the MIT value. For instance, the value settings for adjacent waypoints, such as AVBEP-P154, must account for their traffic interaction characteristics to prevent the propagation of localized congestion. The study further reveals that MIT value should be dynamically adjusted based on real-time traffic data, while historical congestion patterns and traffic prediction analyses provide valuable references for MIT value determination, particularly in regions with periodic congestion. In distributed network flow management, value settings must also consider propagation delays and sector partitioning to ensure the timeliness and consistency of control instructions. By integrating these considerations, MIT value can avoid unnecessary congestion caused by overly restrictive settings or excessive delays due to overly lenient value. This strategy provides valuable insights for the dynamic adjustment of airspace traffic management.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to develop a comprehensive suite of decision support tools for managing flight approaches in multi-airport regions, with a focus on optimizing the implementation of MIT restrictions at appropriate waypoints. We propose a two-stage framework for MIT prediction. The first stage forecasts the need for MIT and determines the waypoints for implementing the restrictions. Building upon the first stage's results, the second stage applies the waypoint combination as a key input to further predict the MIT value for each waypoint under restrictions. A comparative analysis with the single-step LSTM model for direct MIT value prediction revealed significant improvements in evaluation metrics across the four critical waypoints. Specifically, the macro-averaged precision, recall, and F1 scores demonstrated average enhancements of 6.455%, 10.245%, and 10.254%, respectively. These empirical results substantiate the critical role of first-stage output (Task III) in optimizing the predictive

capability of the second-stage model. Our analysis reveals that MIT restrictions are more frequently issued at high-traffic, bottlenecked waypoints, with the demand at arrival airports influencing their issuance. Additionally, other flow control measures, such as GDP, contribute to the MIT decision-making process. The combination of specific waypoints significantly influences the determination of MIT values. MIT values should be dynamically adjusted in response to real-time traffic data, while historical congestion patterns and traffic forecasting can offer valuable insights into the determination of these values. The proposed two-stage prediction model enhances the efficiency of MIT implementation in multi-airport regions, laying a scientific foundation for air traffic flow management in complex airspace systems.

In this study, our predictive analysis predominantly concentrated on MIT-regulated waypoints near landing airports, which, while providing valuable insights, but inadvertently ignoring the impact that other waypoints have on flight landings. Furthermore, our two-stage MIT prediction model is trained on historical MIT decisions made by human experts, which might not always deliver the optimal solution under specific conditions. Moving forward, our research will adopt a broader framework, expanding our analysis to include additional multi-airport regions and examining the intricate relationships between various waypoints. This expansion aims to broaden our study from localized airport clusters to a national scale, enabling dynamic, real-time MIT predictions. Through these advanced modeling efforts, we expect to significantly enhance the accuracy of MIT allocations, decrease unnecessary flight delays, and improve overall air traffic management efficiency. Our objective is to offer strong, empirically supported guidance for traffic management and scheduling decisions across the aviation industry, thereby supporting ongoing efforts to optimize operational efficiency and safety.

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